

1 **Reporting Quality of Systematic Review Protocols in Environmental and**
2 **Occupational Toxicology: A meta-epidemiology study**

3

4 **Authors:**

5 Milica D. Pavlovic^{1†}, Malgorzata Lagisz^{2,3}, Natália B. Videira⁴, Julia M. L. Menon⁵, Gunn
6 E. Vist⁶, Elma Omeragic⁷, Rebecca L. Morgan^{8,9}, Sebastian Hoffmann^{10†}, Evidence-
7 Based Toxicology Collaboration¹¹

8 ¹ Human Toxicology Program, Graduate College, University of Iowa, Iowa City,
9 IA, USA

10 ² Evolution & Ecology Research Centre and School of Biological, Earth and
11 Environmental Sciences, University of New South Wales, Sydney, NSW 2052,
12 Australia

13 ³ Department of Biological Sciences, University of Alberta, CW 405, Biological
14 Sciences Building, Edmonton, AB T6G 2E9, Canada

15 ⁴ Affyglity Solutions - 390 Interlocken Crescent, Broomfield, CO 80021, USA

16 ⁵ Preclinicaltrials.eu, Netherlands Heart Institute, Utrecht, the Netherlands

17 ⁶ Division of Health Services, Norwegian Institute of Public Health, Oslo, Norway

18 ⁷ University of Sarajevo-Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Sarajevo, Sarajevo,
19 Bosnia and Herzegovina

20 ⁸ School of Medicine, Case Western Reserve University, Cleveland, OH, USA

21 ⁹ Department of Health Research, Evidence and Impact, McMaster University
22 Hamilton ON, Canada

23 ¹⁰ Evidence-based Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC), Johns Hopkins University,
24 Bloomberg School of Public Health, Baltimore, MD, USA

25 ¹¹ John Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, John Hopkins University,
26 Baltimore, MD, USA

27

28

29 †Corresponding authors: milica-pavlovic@uiowa.edu and Sebastian Hoffmann
30 sebastian.hoffmann@seh-cs.com

31 **Abstract**

32 **Background:** Systematic reviews (SRs) are increasingly used in toxicology to inform
33 regulatory decisions and research prioritization. SR protocols (SRPs), which outline
34 planned methods in advance, are essential for ensuring transparency and
35 reproducibility. However, little is known about the extent and reporting quality of peer-
36 reviewed protocols in environmental and occupational toxicology.

37 **Objective:** To assess publishing trends, characteristics, and reporting quality of SRPs
38 published in peer-reviewed journals within the fields of environmental and occupational
39 toxicology.

40 **Methods:** We searched four databases (PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, EMBASE)
41 using predefined search strings to identify peer-reviewed SRPs examining the health
42 effects of environmental or occupational exposures. Deduplication was performed in R.
43 Protocols were screened independently by two reviewers using eligibility criteria based
44 on the Population - Concept - Context (PCC) framework. Data extraction included
45 bibliographic details, exposures, outcomes, evidence streams, and use of reporting
46 checklists. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze publication trends and protocol
47 characteristics. Reporting quality was assessed using a 15-item PRISMA-P-based tool,
48 eleven of which were used to assess reporting quality.

49 **Results:** We identified 3,787 records and included 37 peer-reviewed SRPs. These
50 protocols were published between 2014 and 2024, with a peak in 2021. Most protocols
51 focused on environmental toxicology (65%). Academic institutions served as the primary
52 affiliations (76%), and most protocols targeted human evidence (78%). Air pollutants
53 were the most common exposures, and the most frequently studied outcomes involved
54 the nervous, respiratory, and female reproductive systems. Twenty-nine protocols (78%)
55 mentioned using a reporting guideline, mostly PRISMA-P. All studies reported funding
56 sources, but only 32% described the funder's role. Twelve (32%) protocols met all 11
57 minimal reporting quality criteria. Protocols most often underreport data management
58 procedures (27%), confidence in cumulative evidence (73%), and data
59 collection/extraction processes (76%). In contrast, more than 90% of protocols reported
60 review rationale, information sources, and study selection process.

61

62 **Conclusions:** A limited number of peer-reviewed protocols have been published in
63 environmental and occupational toxicology. In general, the peer-reviewed protocols
64 address the minimum reporting requirements. Further research is needed to evaluate
65 methodological quality in greater detail, how closely systematic reviews adhere to their
66 pre-published protocols, and to expand the assessment to SRPs published in the grey
67 literature.

68 **Keywords:** systematic review protocols, toxicology, evidence-based toxicology,
69 reporting quality(Hartung & Tsaion, 2024)

70 **Registration:** 10.5281/zenodo.18187257

71 **1. Background**

72 Systematic reviews (SRs), an evidence-based toxicology tool, are increasingly used to
73 systematically identify, evaluate, and synthesize the available evidence addressing
74 specific toxicological questions (Hartung & Tsaion, 2024; Senerth et al., 2024; Woodruff
75 & Sutton, 2014). By integrating findings across multiple studies, SRs support regulatory
76 decision-making, identify knowledge gaps, guide future research priorities, and inform
77 the efficient allocation of research resources (Farhat et al., 2022; Hoffmann et al., 2017;
78 Wikoff & Fitch, 2024)

79 A key component of SR workflows is the development of a systematic review protocol
80 (SRP) that outlines the research plans and describes the methods to be applied before
81 the review (Moher et al., 2009; Senerth et al., 2024). SRPs are crucial for minimizing
82 duplication of research (Moher, 2013; Siontis et al., 2013), facilitating proactive planning
83 and anticipation of potential challenges, ensuring methodological validity, enabling
84 replication of the review when necessary, and preventing arbitrary decision-making
85 (Andrade et al., 2019; Du et al., 2022; Hardwicke & Wagenmakers, 2023; Shamseer et
86 al., 2015; Stewart et al., 2012; K. van der Braak et al., 2023).

87 Public availability of protocols is considered a major indicator of SR methodological
88 quality, according to A Measurement Tool to Assess Systematic Reviews (AMSTAR-2)
89 (Shea et al., 2017). SR protocols (SRPs) are typically made publicly available either
90 through registration on online platforms (e.g., Zenodo, OSF, Figshare, PROSPERO,
91 protocols.io) or as peer-reviewed publication in scientific journals (Pieper & Rombey,
92 2022). Compared to peer-reviewed protocols, the advantage of registered protocols is

93 rapid, free public dissemination (Andrade et al., 2019). However, the lack of global
94 searchability and the absence of peer-review evaluation are the main drawbacks of
95 protocols available on online registration platforms (Schiavo, 2019; Tawfik et al., 2020;
96 Kim Van Der Braak et al., 2023)

97 Despite recognition of the importance of publicly available SRPs, this step is frequently
98 omitted in the SR process (Kusala Pussegoda et al., 2017). Previous studies show that
99 only a small proportion of SRs report protocol information, with some as low as 6% (102
100 / 1741) (Kusala Pussegoda et al., 2017; K. van der Braak et al., 2023). Most are
101 registered in PROSPERO, which does not include traditional journal-style peer review
102 (Andrade et al., 2019; Van Der Braak et al., 2022). Another study conducted by Menon
103 et al. (2022) analyzed the methodological quality of a limited sample of SRs in
104 environmental health and revealed that only 17% of the reviewed SRs had identifiable
105 SRP, all registered in PROSPERO (Menon et al., 2022). Similarly, ten years ago, less
106 than 10% of reviews in environmental epidemiology reported a registered or published
107 protocol (Sheehan & Lam, 2015).

108 Because the quality of SRPs in environmental and occupational toxicology remains
109 poorly characterized, we assessed their reporting quality following our previously
110 published protocol (Pavlovic et al., 2025). Following our previously published protocol,
111 we predefined the search strategy, study selection, data extraction, and analysis.
112 Reporting quality was operationalized as completeness of reporting, measured by
113 adherence to essential elements derived from the PRISMA-P checklist (Shamseer et al.,
114 2015).

115

116 **Objective**

117 The objective of this meta-epidemiological study was to assess the reporting quality of
118 protocols that evaluate the health effects of exposures in environmental and
119 occupational toxicology, which were published in peer-reviewed journals.

120

121 In line with our objective, we have three research questions:

122

- 123 1. What is the number and yearly distribution of environmental and occupational
124 toxicology protocols published in peer-reviewed journals?

- 125 2. What are the characteristics (bibliographical data, evidence types, field of study,
 126 and guidelines/checklists used for developing the protocol) of those protocols?
 127 3. What is the reporting quality of the protocols?

128 **2. Methods**

129 This study followed established reporting guidelines for meta-epidemiology research
 130 (Murad & Wang, 2017). Detailed methodology was reported in the previously published
 131 protocol (Pavlovic et al., 2025) and registered on Zenodo (10.5281/zenodo.14269983).
 132 This study was reported following the PRISMA-A (2020), PRISMA-S (2020), and the
 133 adapted PRISMA reporting checklist developed for meta-epidemiology studies (Page et
 134 al., 2021; Rethlefsen et al., 2021; Shamseer et al., 2015). Filled checklists are available
 135 in Supplementary Material, in Appendices A.1, A.2, and A.3, respectively.

136 **2.1 Eligibility Criteria**

137 We used the Population - Concept - Context (PCC) framework (see *Table 1*), as per
 138 the methodological guide (Peters et al., 2020) to structure the eligibility criteria, following
 139 the published protocol (Pavlovic et al., 2025).

140

141 **Table 1.** *Eligibility Criteria are presented using the PCC framework.*

PCC	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Population	Systematic Review Protocols (SRP), meta-analysis protocols that self-identified as such in their title	Protocols for other types of reviews, such as umbrella reviews - e.g., protocol of a Systematic Review of SR or meta-analyses Scoping Review Protocols Methodological and experimental protocols
Concept	Assessment of health effects of chemicals or chemical mixtures due to exposures OR	Assessment of health effects of chemicals or chemical mixtures due to <u>intentional</u> exposures OR Assessment of exposures only OR

	Assessment of associations between exposures to chemical or chemical mixtures and health effects.	Aiming to mitigate, remediate, or prevent exposures/effects of exposures
Context	Occupational or environmental toxicology	Other fields of toxicology: safety pharmacology, toxicology of compounds, mixtures (chemical, biological), or extracts/preparations (e.g., herbal medicine) intended to prevent, treat, and diagnose diseases (drugs) or medical devices for human or animal use (veterinary drugs); toxicology of biological and physical hazards; forensic toxicology; analytical toxicology; clinical toxicology; ecotoxicology; toxicology of psychoactive controlled substances.
Types of evidence source	Peer-reviewed journal articles	Abstracts from conferences Gray literature (e.g., PROSPERO protocols)

142

143

144 **2.2 Search and study selection**

145 We followed a pre-validated PRISMA-S-compliant search strategy for the four databases
 146 PubMed.com, Scopus.com, Embase.com, and Core Collection of the Web of Science
 147 platform (see Appendices B.1, B.2, and B.3 of the published protocol (Pavlovic et al.,
 148 2025). Records published in the English language and those published in languages
 149 other than English that can be located by English-language searches were included in
 150 our search.

151 Searches were conducted on December 6th, 2024. In executing the search strategy, no
 152 limitations or filters were used. Duplicate records were removed in R, using ‘tidyverse’
 153 and ‘synthesisr’ packages (Westgate, 2019; Wickham et al., 2019). Following
 154 deduplication in R v.4.2.3 (R Core Team, 2023), a library of records was imported into

155 Covidence (Covidence, 2024). The code is available on Zenodo:
156 10.5281/zenodo.18187257

157 Title / abstract and full-text screening were conducted in Covidence by four reviewers
158 (MPA, SEH, NVI, GVI) in duplicates. Any disagreements were resolved during the
159 meetings, and if no resolution could be achieved, a third reviewer was consulted. The list
160 of excluded records, as well as included protocols, is available in Appendix B.2 and B.3,
161 respectively.

162

163 **2.3 Data Extraction**

164 Data extraction was conducted by four reviewers (SEH, MPA, GVI, EOM) in duplicate in
165 Covidence. Due to the high sensitivity of the software, even minor differences (e.g.,
166 spaces, capital letters) were flagged, and they were resolved by MPA. For the critical
167 difference (e.g., chemical mixture), a discussion meeting was organized, and a third
168 reviewer was advised if the conflict could not be resolved appropriately.

169 The following information was collected related to study characteristics:

- 170 ● General information, including study DOI, title, journal name, first author's
171 location, and affiliation,
- 172 ● The field of study is categorized as occupational, environmental toxicology, or
173 other.
- 174 ● The evidence streams are categorized as studies involving human subjects,
175 animal studies, new approach methodologies, or others,
- 176 ● The exposure to identify the chemicals or chemical mixtures studied (free text),
- 177 ● The adverse health outcome(s) specified (free text),
- 178 ● The guideline or checklist used, if any.

179 The reporting quality in the context of this study was assessed as adherence to minimal
180 reporting items based on the PRISMA-P checklist (Shamseer et al., 2015). PRISMA-P
181 2015 was selected as a well-established reporting checklist for SRPs developed
182 primarily in the context of health care SR. Thus, we modified the PRISMA-P items by
183 excluding, merging, and rephrasing items using terminology that we expected to be
184 more common in a toxicological context. Details are specified in Pavlovic et al. 2025,
185 and the modified PRISMA-P used for assessment is available in Table 2.

186 The items were subdivided into those not directly related (A1-A4, e.g., protocol
 187 registration) and directly related to reporting quality (Q1-Q11, e.g., confidence in
 188 cumulative evidence). The reporting assessments were conducted in Covidence by two
 189 independent assessors (MPA/SEH). Any disagreement was discussed at the meeting,
 190 and if no resolution was achieved, the third reviewer’s opinion was sought (GVI).

191 **Table 2.** *Adapted PRISMA-P 2015 checklist used for assessment of completeness of*
 192 *reporting for both administrative (A1-A4) and quality-related items (Q1-Q11)*

Item	Assessment option and coding (in brackets)
A1. Registration	Reported (1) if the name of the register and a unique document identifier are provided.
	Not reported (0) otherwise
A2. Author contributions	Reported (1) if the contribution of each author is indicated.
	Not reported (0) otherwise
A3. Funder and/or sponsor information*	Reported (1) if funder and/or sponsor information is provided or if it is stated that no funding was received. Minimum data has to include the full name of the funding source and grant number, in case of federal or state funding agencies, foundations, and non-governmental organizations, and/or sponsor name
	Not reported (0) otherwise
A4. Role of funder and/or sponsor	Not applicable (NA) if no funding was received AND no sponsor was indicated.
	Reported (1) if funder and/or sponsor involvement is described.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q1. Rationale	Reported (1) if the topic importance and the necessity of the review are described.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q2. Objectives	Reported (1) if a key element framing, such as (e.g. PECO: population, exposure, comparison, and outcomes) is provided. Note: The information may be provided in a dedicated sub-chapter or in the context of the eligibility criteria.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q3. Eligibility criteria	Reported (1) if criteria related to the individual key elements are reported. For each key element not addressed, a justification is provided.

	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q4. Information sources	Reported (1) if databases OR other resources (e.g., websites) are stated.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q5. Search strategy	Reported (1) if the search string, incl. limitations, if applicable, for at least one database is provided.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q6. Data management	Reported (1) if the data management software/web-based platform to be used in search, study selection, and data extraction/assessment is indicated
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q7. Selection process	Reported (1) if the procedure for inclusion of studies (i.e., number of independent reviewers AND conflict resolution) is stated.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q8. Data collection and extraction process	Reported (1) if the procedure for extracting data (i.e., number of independent reviewers AND conflict resolution) AND a list of all data items expected to be collected is provided.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q9. Risk of bias criteria	Reported (1) if a tool or criteria are stated, AND if the procedure for assessing risk of bias, AND if the procedure for accounting for the risk of bias in the analysis is stated. If the authors modified existing tools, the modifications are described.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q10. Data synthesis	Reported (1) if the methods for presenting data (e.g., tabular summary, meta-analysis) are stated. If different evidence streams are addressed, a description of how these will be handled (e.g., integrated) is described.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.
Q11. Confidence in cumulative evidence	Reported (1) if an assessment of the certainty of all evidence (e.g., using GRADE) is described.
	Not reported (0) otherwise.

193

194 After extraction, an Excel file with the data was downloaded from Covidence and used
195 for data analysis.

196 **2.4 Data Analysis**

197 The exported data related to bibliographic information and study characteristics were
198 summarized using trend lines and bar graphs that were made in GraphPad Prism, and in
199 tabular format.

200 Due to the complexity of exposures and outcomes collected and to improve data
201 reporting and facilitate analysis, MPA performed categorization and grouping of these
202 two characteristics, followed by a second reviewer assessment (SEH). The grouping of
203 exposures and outcomes was performed in Excel, and the data are available in
204 Appendix B.4 and B.5 of the Supplementary Material, respectively.

205 Exposure agents were classified as air pollutants, industrial chemicals, pesticides,
206 metals, pharmaceuticals, cosmetic ingredients, and mycotoxins. For example, all studies
207 whose exposures fulfilled the World Health Organization (WHO) definition of air pollution
208 were classified as such (WHO, 2024). Confirmation for the air pollutants category was
209 performed using the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) Hazardous Airborne
210 Pollutants (HAPs) list (Agency, 2025). Other distinct categories were established based
211 on predominant use, regulatory oversight, and classification (e.g., pesticides,
212 pharmaceuticals, metals, industrial chemicals).

213 Similarly, the outcomes were classified by the target organ system. Where more than
214 one organ system was assessed, we categorized the outcome as multiple systems.
215 When the outcome was not specific to the organ system (e.g., genotoxicity or systemic
216 toxicity), we used the category unspecified. For disease-related outcomes involving
217 multiple organ systems, we used the ICD-11 organ system classification for the disease
218 itself (WHO, 2022).

219 For reporting assessment items, administrative (A1 - A4) and reporting quality-related
220 items (Q1 - Q11) were all used for data visualization. The response options were
221 'reported', coded as '1', and 'not reported', coded as '0', or N/A in case the item is not
222 applicable.

223 The reporting quality of an individual protocol was summarized using the items Q1 to
224 Q11 with an identical binary response format. The reporting quality of an individual
225 protocol is expressed as a percentage of reporting items coded as '1' (**q**). Assessment of
226 the individual quality items was summarized as the percentage (**p**) of 'reporting items

227 coded as '1' across all protocols assessed for that item. Detailed formulas are available
228 in the published protocol (Pavlovic et al., 2025). Calculations of q and p are available in
229 Appendix B.7 in Supplementary Material.

230 **2.5 Deviations from the Protocol**

231 Grouping of exposures and outcomes was not previously described in the protocol and
232 was done to facilitate data analysis, as described in 2.4.1. For visualization of reporting
233 quality, we used the traffic light method instead of a histogram. The traffic light was
234 made in Excel and is available in Appendix B.7 of the Supplementary Material. We
235 additionally analyzed whether published protocols provided the PRISMA-P checklist in
236 Appendix B.3 of the Supplementary Material (MPA, JM). We did not make a comparison
237 between our reporting assessment and the authors' self-reported PRISMA-P checklist
238 items. This *post-hoc* analysis was briefly discussed in the Results and Discussion
239 section. Due to the limited number of protocols included in this study, observed trends
240 (e.g., correlation between use of checklist and journal) were only briefly discussed in the
241 Discussion and not part of the Results.

242 **3. Results**

243 **3.1 Study Selection**

244 After deduplication ($n = 3,787$), 3,733 records (98.6%) were excluded during title and
245 abstract screening. Fifty-four full texts were assessed, and 17 were excluded based on
246 population, concept, context, or evidence type, resulting in 37 protocols included for
247 analysis. The list of included and excluded records and protocols is available in
248 Appendix B of the Supplementary Material. The study selection process is depicted in
249 the PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 1).

250

251 **Figure 1.** PRISMA flow chart of study selection.

252

253 3.2 Number and yearly distribution of protocols

254 The 37 included protocols were published between 2014 and 2024, i.e., until the date of
 255 the search. An increasing trend in the number of published protocols per year was
 256 observed until 2021, after which the yearly numbers dropped (Figure 2A). *Environment*
 257 *International* published the most protocols (11 / 37), followed by *BMJ Open* (7 / 37) and

258 *Systematic Reviews* (4 / 37). Ten journals published three or fewer eligible protocols
 259 each (Figure 2B).

260
 261 **Figure 2.** *Protocols published per year (A) and number of protocols per journal (B).*

262 **3.3 Characteristics of included protocols**

263 Our second objective was to characterize the protocols in terms of bibliographical data,
 264 evidence types, field of study, and guidelines/checklists used. Regionally, most protocols
 265 came from Europe, 41% (15 / 37). Country-specific data showed that most protocols
 266 originated from China, 16% (6 / 37), followed by the United States, 11% (4 / 37).

267 Overall characteristics of the included protocols are summarized in Table 2. The first
 268 authors of 28 of the 37 protocols were affiliated with academia, while the others were
 269 affiliated with governments, international organizations (e.g., WHO), or industry. Our
 270 data also show that the topics covered by SRPs are mostly related to the field of
 271 environmental toxicology, 65% (24 / 37). Seven protocols addressed an occupational
 272 toxicology topic, 19% (7 / 37), and interestingly, six protocols considered both exposure
 273 scenarios. The majority of protocols, 78% (29/37) were focused on human studies; two
 274 were using only animal studies as the evidence source, and six were deriving their
 275 conclusions from at least two different sources, including human-related studies, animal
 276 studies, and/or new approach methodologies (NAMs).

277 Looking at the exposures intended to be investigated, we found that most studies
 278 focused on the association between air pollution and health outcomes, with the majority

279 examining ambient (outdoor) air pollutants, 70% (9 / 13). Persistent organic pollutants
 280 (as defined by the Stockholm Convention) were the most investigated industrial
 281 chemicals, 71% (5 / 7), followed by plasticizers like bisphenol-A, and aromatic amines
 282 such as benzidine and beta-naphthylamine. Pesticides in four studies, while three
 283 studies addressed heavy metals.

284 Our analysis showed that a broad range of outcomes was addressed. Most studied
 285 outcomes were related to the nervous and respiratory system, 19% (7 / 37 each).
 286 Endpoints related to the female reproductive system, 16% (6 / 37), were significantly
 287 more represented compared to the male reproductive system, 3% (1 / 37). An equal
 288 number of protocols assessed the effects of exposure on pregnancy-related outcomes
 289 involving embryo/fetus 8% (3 / 37), and diseases such as endometriosis and polycystic
 290 ovarian syndrome (PCOS) 8% (3 / 37). The endocrine system, primarily in the context of
 291 metabolic disorders, accounted for 11% of outcomes, followed by the cardiovascular,
 292 hematopoietic, and renal systems.

293 Thirty studies explicitly stated the use of a reporting checklist/guideline for protocol
 294 reporting. The majority mentioned PRISMA-P (70% (26 / 37)), while the remaining three
 295 referred to Recommendations for the conduct of systematic reviews in toxicology and
 296 environmental health research (COSTER) or Reporting standards for Systematic
 297 Evidence Syntheses (ROSES) (Haddaway et al., 2018; Whaley et al., 2020). We further
 298 analyzed whether PRISMA-P was available in the Supplementary Material, and in only
 299 38% (14/37) cases was it accompanied by the document.

300 **Table 3.** *Characteristics of included studies.*

Characteristics	Type	Percentage (Number of protocols / total number)
Field of Study	Environmental	65% (24 / 37)
	Occupational	19% (7 / 37)
	Both	16% (6 / 37)
First author's affiliation	Academia	76% (28 / 37)
	Government	11% (4 / 37)
	Other (non-profit, international organization)	11% (4 / 37)

	Industry	3% (1 / 37)
Type of evidence streams	Human	78% (29 / 37)
	Multiple	16% (6 / 37)
	Animal	5% (2 / 37)
Exposures	Air pollutants	38% (14 / 37)
	Industrial chemicals	19% (7 / 37)
	Pesticides	11% (4 / 37)
	Metals	8% (3 / 37)
	Pharmaceuticals	8% (3 / 37)
	Others (cosmetics, mycotoxins)	5% (2 / 37)
	Unspecified	5% (2 / 37)
	Multiple	5% (2 / 37)
Outcomes per Organ System	Nervous	19% (7 / 37)
	Respiratory	19% (7 / 37)
	Reproductive, female	16% (6 / 37)
	Multiple	16% (6 / 37)
	Endocrine	11% (4 / 37)
	Others (cardiovascular, circulatory, renal)	8% (3 / 37)
	Unspecified	8% (3 / 37)
	Reproductive, male	3% (1 / 37)
Guideline/Checklist	PRISMA-P 2015	70% (26 / 37)
	Not reported	22% (8 / 37)
	Other	5% (2 / 37)
	Combined	3% (1 / 37)

302 **3.4 Completeness of reporting**

303 We assessed the included protocols using 15 criteria, including 4 administrative (A1 -
304 A4) and 11 quality-related (Q1 - Q11) criteria. Results of the assessment of reporting
305 completeness are summarized in Figure 3.

306 In all 37 assessed protocols, authors reported the funder/sponsor, but in only 30% (11 /
307 37) of cases did they report the role of the funder/sponsor. For 81% (30 / 37) of the peer-
308 reviewed protocols published in journals, registration information was also recorded in
309 an external database, usually PROSPERO. Authors' contributions were described in
310 89% (33 / 37) of protocols.

311 When it comes to reporting quality criteria, 32% (12 / 37) of the assessed protocols met
312 all 11 quality criteria, at least at the minimum level captured by PRISMA-P items used.
313 Twenty-seven percent (10 / 37) failed one criterion, in most cases, the criterion 'Data
314 management procedures' due to a lack of software reporting. Nineteen percent (7 / 37)
315 met nine criteria. This means that 78% (29 / 37) of the protocols met more than 81% (≥ 9
316 / 11) of the reporting quality criteria. Commonly omitted items were the data
317 management and collection procedures, and confidence in cumulative evidence. A
318 similar trend was observed in those that met quality criteria for 6 or fewer items, 11% (4 /
319 37). Of the eight protocols meeting 8 or fewer criteria, at least half did not state the
320 objective, did not fully address data management and data collection procedures, and
321 omitted RoB assessment and confidence in cumulative evidence.

322 In relation to reporting quality items, data management procedures 54% (20 / 37), such
323 as software/platforms used for selection, extraction, and analysis, were the most poorly
324 reported items. This was followed by poor reporting in the assessment of 'confidence in
325 cumulative evidence', 73% (27 / 37), and 'data collection and extraction process', which
326 refers to the number of reviewers, conflict resolution, and extraction, 76% (28 / 37).
327 Assessment of 'risk of bias criteria' was adequately reported in 86% (32 / 37) of
328 protocols, and 'eligibility criteria' and 'research objectives' in 89% (33 / 37). 'Search
329 strategy' that includes search strings was reported in 92% (34 / 37) of protocols. The
330 'selection process', which includes the number of reviewers and conflict resolution, was
331 reported in 95% (35 / 37) of protocols. 'Rationale for the study' and 'data synthesis
332 procedures' were described in 97% (36 / 37) of the protocols. The 'sources of
333 information' were provided in all the examined protocols.

334

335 **Figure 3.** Traffic-light plot of the assessment results for 37 published protocols across 25
 336 criteria. Scores: Reported (●), not reported (●), not applicable (○). The overall
 337 reporting quality of individual protocols (q) and individual items (p) is expressed as
 338 percentages (%). Light blue columns represent administrative items, while quality items
 339 are indicated in light yellow columns and included in reporting completeness scores.

340

4. Discussion

341

342 Between 2014 and 2024, a limited number (37) of eligible, peer-reviewed SRPs were
343 identified in our study. Publication rates increased until 2021 before declining, with
344 protocols concentrated in a small number of journals, particularly *Environment*
345 *International*, suggesting that editorial policies may strongly influence protocol
346 publication practices in environmental health (Whaley et al., 2016). Most protocols were
347 published by authors from academia and focused on environmental toxicology, with air
348 pollution as the most common exposure and human health evidence as the dominant
349 evidence base. Overall reporting quality was relatively high when assessed against the
350 adapted PRISMA-P 2015 reporting checklist, with 32% of SRPs meeting all required
351 reporting items. Of all administrative items assessed, role of funder was the most under-
352 reported (30% (11 / 37)). Data management procedures, data extraction processes, and
353 assessment of confidence in cumulative evidence remained poorly reported, indicating
354 that adherence to reporting guidelines does not necessarily ensure complete
355 transparency in key methodological domains.

356 Our findings highlight important issues related to reporting practices and the
357 implementation of methodological standards.

358 The thematic and methodological profiles of protocols indicate that SR activity in
359 toxicology is largely driven by established evidence bases and regulatory relevance
360 (Farhat et al., 2022; Wikoff & Fitch, 2024). The predominance of human health-oriented
361 evidence synthesis, alongside limited incorporation of animal studies and human-based,
362 new approach methodologies (NAMs), suggests that newer or less standardized
363 evidence streams have not yet been fully integrated into systematic evidence synthesis
364 practice (Hooijmans et al., 2018; Krebs et al., 2025; National Academies of Sciences et
365 al., 2023; van der Zalm et al., 2022). The few animal studies were mostly for the purpose
366 of setting occupational exposure limits (Struijs et al., 2023; van Luijk et al., 2019). Only
367 four protocols included evidence from NAMs (Matta et al., 2021; Ramadhan Makame et
368 al., 2023; Uter et al., 2021; Vaccari et al., 2017). The strong focus on air pollution further
369 reflects the maturity of this field, where long-standing epidemiological evidence and
370 policy relevance have enabled sustained use of SRs in decision-making contexts
371 (Forastiere, 2024; Forastiere et al., 2024; Fowler et al., 2020; WHO, 2024). These
372 patterns likely reflect broader structural features of toxicological evidence generation,
373 where research priorities are shaped by public health relevance, regulatory demand, and
374 the availability of funding for primary research (Haby et al., 2025; Norris et al., 2021;

375 Wikoff et al., 2020). In turn, the existence of a robust primary evidence base facilitates
376 further synthesis activity, reinforcing a feedback loop between policy needs, research
377 funding, and evidence generation (Chartres et al., 2025; Hoffmann et al., 2017; Sesin et
378 al., 2023). This dynamic helps explain why SRs cluster in certain exposure domains
379 while remaining limited in emerging or less-established methodological areas.

380 Although most protocols reported using PRISMA-P (70%, 26 / 37) this did not
381 consistently translate into more complete reporting, with some of the lowest-scoring
382 protocols stating adherence to the reporting checklist. Furthermore, only 38% (14 / 37) of
383 those reporting use of PRISMA-P provided the checklist in Supplementary materials.
384 This lack of association between checklist use and reporting completeness suggests a
385 persistent gap between formal endorsement and its practical implementation (Kusala
386 Pussegoda et al., 2017). The dominance of PRISMA-P, which was designed for health
387 and medical studies in general, may stem from the absence of toxicology-specific
388 guidance, as well as its widespread adoption, large user base, and endorsement by
389 journals (Page et al., 2021; Pearson et al., 2025). Interestingly, we observed
390 inconsistencies within the same journal (e.g., *BMJ Open*), with some publications using
391 reporting checklists while others did not (Sarah et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2021)
392 suggesting a lack of uniform editorial practices. Consistent with our findings, the
393 ASPIRE-SCAGE and ASPIRE-UK studies reported modest improvements in adherence
394 to SPIRIT recommendations over time, although reporting remained incomplete overall
395 and important gaps persisted, particularly in investigator- or non-industry-sponsored
396 clinical trial protocols (Gryaznov et al., 2022; Speich et al., 2022). Together, these
397 findings indicate that improving reporting quality requires not only guideline
398 dissemination but also stronger editorial and reviewer enforcement mechanisms
399 (Schlussel et al., 2023).

400 Despite overall high completeness of reporting, important gaps remain in core domains
401 of transparency, such as funding roles, data management procedures, data extraction
402 processes and assessment of certainty in the evidence base. These omissions are
403 important because they limit the interpretability and reproducibility of systematic review
404 protocols and may weaken confidence in subsequent evidence synthesis (Du et al.,
405 2022; Schlussel et al., 2023).

406 Underreporting of funding roles is particularly relevant given evidence that funding
407 structures can influence study design and interpretation in ways that affect research

408 conclusions, as seen in the examples derived from pharmaceutical and food industry
409 (Bes-Rastrollo et al., 2013; Carducci et al., 2018; Rosenberg et al., 2013; Ross et al.,
410 2008).

411 'Data management procedures' (Q6) that included indicating the software used across
412 different study stages were incompletely reported in 54% (20 / 37) of cases. In 76% (28 /
413 37) of cases, the authors did not describe the 'Data extraction' (Q8) procedure in enough
414 detail. This could be partially explained by our assessment approach, where these two
415 items required three conditions to be reported, making it more sensitive to reveal under-
416 reporting.

417 In our study, 70% of SRs reported confidence in cumulative evidence assessment, and
418 interestingly, it was reported in all SRs that included more than two evidence streams.
419 Certainty/confidence of evidence (CoE, formerly quality of evidence) assessment is a
420 fundamental component of SRs because it evaluates the overall confidence that can be
421 placed in a body of evidence by considering domains such as risk of bias, consistency,
422 directness, and precision (Brignardello-Petersen & Guyatt, 2025). Frameworks
423 commonly applied include GRADE and its adaptations in the field of environmental
424 health: the Office of Health Assessment and Translation (OHAT) approach, and the
425 Navigation Guide (Prasad, 2024; Radke et al., 2026; Rooney et al., 2014; Woodruff &
426 Sutton, 2014). The extensive effort of the GRADE Working Group in the field of public
427 and environmental health is summarized elsewhere (Morgan et al., 2019). Transparent
428 reporting of CoE assessment requires clear documentation of the framework used, the
429 domains evaluated, the rationale for each judgment, and the resulting certainty ratings
430 for individual outcomes (Prasad, 2024; Shaheen et al., 2023; Siedler et al., 2024).
431 Underreporting of this process reduces the transparency, reproducibility, and
432 trustworthiness of systematic reviews by obscuring the basis for confidence in the
433 findings and limiting the ability of regulators, policymakers, and other stakeholders to
434 appropriately interpret and apply the evidence in risk assessment and decision-making
435 contexts (Brignardello-Petersen & Guyatt, 2025; Siedler et al., 2024).

436 Overall, these issues appear consistent with patterns observed across other fields of
437 evidence synthesis (Frost et al., 2022; Innocenti et al., 2022; Ivaldi et al., 2024; Panic et
438 al., 2013). The role of funder/sponsor information, confidence in cumulative evidence,
439 and risk of bias were also the items poorly reported for published PubMed-indexed
440 protocols in the study by *Frost et al.*, showing concordance with our results and a pattern

441 present across disciplines, at least in the domain of peer-reviewed literature (Frost et al.,
442 2022).

443 In summary, due to the nature of SRs, most of them cover exposures with a long history
444 of research and outcomes with important public health relevance. Most protocols
445 reported using the PRISMA-P 2015 checklist and adhered to the minimum reporting
446 requirements. However, it seems that there remains considerable room for improvement
447 in relation to how SRPs in toxicology are reported, especially regarding the reporting of
448 'data management procedures' and 'confidence in cumulative evidence'. Although the
449 overall reporting quality of SRPs assessed in this study could be considered good,
450 follow-up studies investigating the appropriateness of how items were addressed and
451 the adherence of SRs to published SRPs are needed; such protocol-paper comparisons
452 have been performed in other fields, for systematic reviews with PROSPERO protocols
453 and published protocols (Hopewell et al., 2002; Hu et al., 2021; Koensgen et al., 2019;
454 Siebert et al., 2023). Importantly, reporting completeness should not be equated with
455 methodological rigor (Faggion Jr, 2023). A protocol may comprehensively report
456 suboptimal or inappropriate methods, while a methodologically robust protocol may
457 nevertheless omit important reporting details (Faggion Jr, 2023; K. Pussegoda et al.,
458 2017). Accordingly, our findings should be interpreted as an assessment of transparency
459 rather than methodological validity. Importantly, reporting completeness should not be
460 equated with methodological rigor.

461 This work provides a foundation for future research and highlights several important
462 avenues for further investigation. Future studies should assess the impact of protocol
463 development and preregistration on the methodological rigor of SRs in environmental
464 health, for example by comparing the methodological quality of reviews with registered
465 or published protocols to those conducted without a protocol. Additionally, comparing the
466 quality of protocols published in registries with those published in peer-reviewed journals
467 would help determine the added value of peer review in improving protocol quality.

468 **Limitations**

469 We are aware that a small number of protocols meeting the inclusion criteria (37) limits
470 our ability to statistically assess the trends. However, we also consider this a finding –
471 that publishing SRPs, in the case of environmental and occupational exposures, in peer-
472 reviewed journals is not widespread among researchers in this field. Also, our approach

473 of checking if certain reporting items were present, but not if they were implemented
474 appropriately, limits the assessment of the quality of the SRPs. While not meeting
475 several of our assessment criteria is a clear indication of low reporting quality, meeting
476 all criteria does not necessarily mean that the protocol is of high quality. For example,
477 describing how RoB was assessed does not imply that a suitable assessment tool was
478 chosen, and providing a search string does not mean that the string is error-free or
479 sufficiently sensitive to retrieve most of the relevant evidence. Our assessment criteria
480 represent minimal reporting requirements, rather than requirements for comprehensive
481 reporting of all relevant methodological details. For example, we scored the search
482 strategy as present if a search string was provided for at least one database; ideally,
483 complete search strings should be provided for all databases used, and they should be
484 benchmarked for retrieval sensitivity via relative recall (Lagisz et al., 2025). Finally, this
485 assessment is relevant at the protocol level but provides limited information on quality at
486 the final publication level; a well-reported protocol does not equate to a rigorous or well-
487 reported SR. Further studies on this topic are warranted, as mentioned in the section
488 above.

489 **5. Conclusions**

490 Overall, our meta-epidemiology study shows a low number of peer-reviewed SRPs
491 published in scientific journals in the field of toxicology. Although the minimum reporting
492 quality was acceptable, improvement in reporting data management, funders/sponsor
493 involvement, and confidence in cumulative evidence could be improved. Further
494 research is needed to assess the quality of protocols in greater detail; to evaluate how
495 closely SRs adhere to their pre-published protocols, to evaluate if SRs with published
496 SRPs are 'better' than those without, and to expand the assessment to SRPs published
497 in grey literature.

498 **Data and code availability statement**

499 The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo, DOI:
500 10.5281/zenodo.18187257.

501 **Contributions**

502 Conceptualization: Milica D. Pavlovic, Malgorzata Lagisz, Natália B. Videira, Julia M. L.
503 Menon, Gunn E. Vist, Rebecca L. Morgan, Sebastian Hoffmann.

504 Data collection/acquisition: Milica Pavlovic, Malgorzata Lagisz, Natalia Videira, Gunn E.
505 Vist, Sebastian Hoffmann, Elma Omeragic
506 Data curation: Milica D. Pavlovic, Natália B. Videira, Gunn E. Vist, Sebastian Hoffmann.
507 Formal analysis: Milica D. Pavlovic
508 Funding acquisition: not applicable
509 Methodology: Milica D. Pavlovic, Malgorzata Lagisz, Natália B. Videira, Julia M. L.
510 Menon, Gunn E. Vist, Elma Omeragic, Rebecca L. Morgan, Sebastian Hoffmann.
511 Project administration: Milica D. Pavlovic and Sebastian Hoffmann.
512 Resources: Sebastian Hoffmann.
513 Software: Gunn E. Vist.
514 Supervision: Sebastian Hoffmann and Milica D. Pavlovic.
515 Writing - original draft: Milica D. Pavlovic, Sebastian Hoffmann, and Julia M. L. Menon.
516 Writing - review & editing: Milica D. Pavlovic, Malgorzata Lagisz, Natália B. Videira, Julia
517 M. L. Menon, Gunn E. Vist, Elma Omeragic, and Rebecca L. Morgan, Sebastian
518 Hoffmann.

519 **Funding**

520 This project did not receive any direct funding.

521 **Disclosure statement**

522 The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

523 **Supplementary Material:**

524 **Appendix A - Reporting checklists**

- 525 ● A.1 - PRISMA - A (2020)
- 526 ● A.2 - PRISMA - S (2020)
- 527 ● A.3 - Adapted PRISMA (2017) checklist for meta-epidemiology study

528 **Appendix B**

- 529 ● B.1 - metadata
- 530 ● B.2 - List of Excluded Records
- 531 ● B.3 - List of Included Records
- 532 ● B.4 - Exposure
- 533 ● B.5 - Outcome

- 534 • B.6 - Quality Assessment
- 535 • B.7 - Summary of Quality Assessment
- 536

537 **References:**

- 538 Andrade, R., Pereira, R., Weir, A., Ardern, C. L., & Espregueira-Mendes, J. (2019). Zombie reviews
 539 taking over the PROSPERO systematic review registry. It's time to fight back! *British*
 540 *Journal of Sports Medicine*, 53(15), 919. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2017-098252>
- 541 Bes-Rastrollo, M., Schulze, M. B., Ruiz-Canela, M., & Martinez-Gonzalez, M. A. (2013). Financial
 542 conflicts of interest and reporting bias regarding the association between sugar-
 543 sweetened beverages and weight gain: a systematic review of systematic reviews. *PLoS*
 544 *Med*, 10(12), e1001578; discussion e1001578.
 545 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1001578>
- 546 Brignardello-Petersen, R., & Guyatt, G. H. (2025). Assessing the certainty of the evidence in
 547 systematic reviews: importance, process, and use. *American Journal of Epidemiology*,
 548 194(6), 1681-1686. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwae332>
- 549 Carducci, B., Oh, C., Keats, E. C., Gaffey, M. F., Roth, D. E., & Bhutta, Z. A. (2018). PROTOCOL:
 550 Impact of the food environment on diet-related health outcomes in school-age children
 551 and adolescents in low- and middle-income countries: a systematic review. *Campbell*
 552 *Syst Rev*, 14(1), Jan-55.
- 553 Chartres, N., Aung, M. T., Norris, S. L., Cooper, C., Bero, L. A., Chou, R., Payne-Sturges, D. C.,
 554 Wagner, W. E., Reyes, J. W., Askie, L. M., Axelrad, D. A., Vigo, D. F., Johnston, J. E., Lam,
 555 J., Nachman, K. E., Rehfuess, E., Rothschild, R., Sutton, P., Zeise, L., & Woodruff, T. J.
 556 (2025). Development of the Navigation Guide Evidence-to-Decision Framework for
 557 Environmental Health: Version 1.0. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 59(9),
 558 4230-4244. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.4c08063>
- 559 Du, K. J., Li, G. S., Zhang, K., Lin, Y., Yang, F., & Moher, D. (2022). Prof. David Moher: Guidelines
 560 for Reporting Health Research (A User's Manual). *Ann Transl Med*, 10(17), 944.
 561 <https://doi.org/10.21037/atm-2022-24>
- 562 Faggion Jr, C. M. (2023). Methodological quality, risk of bias, and reporting quality: A confusion
 563 persists. *Journal of Evidence-Based Medicine*, 16(3), 261-263.
 564 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/jebm.12550>
- 565 Farhat, N., Tsaoun, K., Saunders-Hastings, P., Morgan, R. L., Ramoju, S., Hartung, T., & Krewski,
 566 D. (2022). Systematic review in evidence-based risk assessment. *ALTEX*, 39(3), 463-479.
 567 <https://doi.org/10.14573/altex.2004111>
- 568 Forastiere, F. (2024). Revisiting Decades of Research on Air Pollution and Acute Lower
 569 Respiratory Infections. *Annals of the American Thoracic Society*, 1124–1126.
 570 <https://doi.org/10.1513/annalsats.202405-547ed>
- 571 Forastiere, F., Orru, H., Krzyzanowski, M., & Spadaro, J. V. (2024). The last decade of air pollution
 572 epidemiology and the challenges of quantitative risk assessment. *Environmental Health*,
 573 23(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-024-01136-5>
- 574 Fowler, D., Brimblecombe, P., Burrows, J., Heal, M. R., Grennfelt, P., Stevenson, D. S., Jowett, A.,
 575 Nemitz, E., Coyle, M., Liu, X., Chang, Y., Fuller, G. W., Sutton, M. A., Klimont, Z.,
 576 Unsworth, M. H., & Vienne, M. (2020). A chronology of global air quality. *Philosophical*
 577 *Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*,
 578 378(2183), 20190314. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2019.0314>

579 Frost, A. D., Hróbjartsson, A., & Nejtgaard, C. H. (2022). Adherence to the PRISMA-P 2015
580 reporting guideline was inadequate in systematic review protocols. *Journal of Clinical*
581 *Epidemiology*, *150*, 179-187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2022.07.002>

582 Gryaznov, D., von Niederhäusern, B., Speich, B., Kasenda, B., Ojeda-Ruiz, E., Blümle, A.,
583 Schandelmaier, S., Mertz, D., Odutayo, A., Tomonaga, Y., Amstutz, A., Pauli-Magnus, C.,
584 Gloy, V., Lohner, S., Bischoff, K., Wollmann, K., Rehner, L., Meerpohl, J. J., Nordmann,
585 A.,...Briel, M. (2022). Reporting quality of clinical trial protocols: a repeated cross-
586 sectional study about the Adherence to SPIrit Recommendations in Switzerland, CANada
587 and GERmany (ASPIRE-SCAGE). *BMJ Open*, *12*(5), e053417.
588 <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2021-053417>

589 Haby, M. M., Reveiz, L., Thomas, R., & Jordan, H. (2025). An integrated framework to guide
590 evidence-informed public health policymaking. *Journal of Public Health Policy*, *46*(1),
591 193-210. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41271-024-00535-9>

592 Haddaway, N. R., Macura, B., Whaley, P., & Pullin, A. S. (2018). ROSES RepORting standards for
593 Systematic Evidence Syntheses: pro forma, flow-diagram and descriptive summary of
594 the plan and conduct of environmental systematic reviews and systematic maps.
595 *Environmental Evidence*, *7*(1), 7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-018-0121-7>

596 Hardwicke, T. E., & Wagenmakers, E.-J. (2023). Reducing bias, increasing transparency and
597 calibrating confidence with preregistration. *Nature Human Behaviour*, *7*(1), 15-26.
598 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-022-01497-2>

599 Hartung, T., & Tsaïoun, K. (2024). Evidence-based approaches in toxicology: their origins,
600 challenges, and future directions. *Evidence-Based Toxicology*, *2*(1), 2421187.
601 <https://doi.org/10.1080/2833373X.2024.2421187>

602 Hoffmann, S., De Vries, R. B. M., Stephens, M. L., Beck, N. B., Dirven, H. A. A. M., Fowle, J. R.,
603 Goodman, J. E., Hartung, T., Kimber, I., Lalu, M. M., Thayer, K., Whaley, P., Wikoff, D., &
604 Tsaïoun, K. (2017). A primer on systematic reviews in toxicology. *Archives of Toxicology*,
605 *91*(7), 2551-2575. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00204-017-1980-3>

606 Hooijmans, C. R., de Vries, R. B. M., Ritskes-Hoitinga, M., Rovers, M. M., Leeflang, M. M.,
607 IntHout, J., Wever, K. E., Hooft, L., de Beer, H., Kuijpers, T., Macleod, M. R., Sena, E. S.,
608 Ter Riet, G., Morgan, R. L., Thayer, K. A., Rooney, A. A., Guyatt, G. H., Schünemann, H. J.,
609 & Langendam, M. W. (2018). Facilitating healthcare decisions by assessing the certainty
610 in the evidence from preclinical animal studies. *PLOS ONE*, *13*(1), e0187271.
611 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0187271>

612 Hopewell, S., Middleton, P., & Silagy, C. (2002). Publishing Protocols of Systematic Reviews:
613 Comparing What Was Done to What Was Planned. *Jama*, *287*(21), 2831-2834.

614 Hu, K., Zhao, L., Zhou, Q., Mei, F., Gao, Q., Chen, F., Jiang, M., Zhao, B., Zhang, W., Kwong, J. S.
615 W., Ma, Y., Mou, C., & Ma, B. (2021). Inconsistencies in study eligibility criteria are
616 common between non-Cochrane systematic reviews and their protocols registered in
617 PROSPERO. *Research Synthesis Methods*, *12*(3), 394-405.
618 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1476>

619 Innocenti, T., Feller, D., Giagio, S., Salvioli, S., Minnucci, S., Brindisino, F., Cosentino, C., Piano, L.,
620 Chiarotto, A., & Ostelo, R. (2022). Adherence to the PRISMA statement and its
621 association with risk of bias in systematic reviews published in rehabilitation journals: A
622 meta-research study. *Braz J Phys Ther*, *26*(5), 100450.
623 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjpt.2022.100450>

624 Ivaldi, D., Burgos, M., Oltra, G., Liquitay, C. E., & Garegnani, L. (2024). Adherence to PRISMA
625 2020 statement assessed through the expanded checklist in systematic reviews of

626 interventions: A meta-epidemiological study. *Cochrane Evidence Synthesis and Methods*,
627 2(5). <https://doi.org/10.1002/cesm.12074>

628 Koensgen, N., Rombey, T., Allers, K., Mathes, T., Hoffmann, F., & Pieper, D. (2019). Comparison
629 of non-Cochrane systematic reviews and their published protocols: differences occurred
630 frequently but were seldom explained. *J Clin Epidemiol*, 110, 34-41.
631 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2019.02.012>

632 Krebs, C. E., Geissler, S., Herrmann, K., Kandaras, K., Kavanagh, O., Langan, L. M., Pistollato, F.,
633 Raha, S., Tripodi, I. J., & Trunnell, E. R. (2025). Exploring animal methods bias in
634 biomedical research funding: Workshop proceedings and action steps. *NAM Journal*, 1,
635 100004. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.namjnl.2024.100004>

636 Lagisz, M., Yang, Y., Young, S., & Nakagawa, S. (2025). A practical guide to evaluating sensitivity
637 of literature search strings for systematic reviews using relative recall. *Research*
638 *Synthesis Methods*, 16(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1017/rsm.2024.6>

639 Matta, K., Koual, M., Ploteau, S., Coumoul, X., Audouze, K., Le Bizec, B., Antignac, J. P., & Cano-
640 Sancho, G. (2021). Associations between Exposure to Organochlorine Chemicals and
641 Endometriosis: A Systematic Review of Experimental Studies and Integration of
642 Epidemiological Evidence. *Environ Health Perspect*, 129(7), 76003.
643 <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP8421>

644 Menon, J. M. L., Struijs, F., & Whaley, P. (2022). The methodological rigour of systematic reviews
645 in environmental health. *Crit Rev Toxicol*, 52(3), 167-187.
646 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408444.2022.2082917>

647 Moher, D. (2013). The problem of duplicate systematic reviews. *BMJ : British Medical Journal*,
648 347, f5040. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.f5040>

649 Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., & Altman, D. G. (2009). Preferred Reporting Items for
650 Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses: The PRISMA Statement. *PLoS Medicine*, 6(7),
651 e1000097. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1000097>

652 Morgan, R. L., Beverly, B., Ghersi, D., Schünemann, H. J., Rooney, A. A., Whaley, P., Zhu, Y. G., &
653 Thayer, K. A. (2019). GRADE guidelines for environmental and occupational health: A
654 new series of articles in Environment International. *Environ Int*, 128, 11-12.
655 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2019.04.016>

656 Murad, M. H., & Wang, Z. (2017). Guidelines for reporting meta-epidemiological methodology
657 research. *Evidence Based Medicine*, 22(4), 139-142. <https://doi.org/10.1136/ebmed-2017-110713>

658

659 National Academies of Sciences, E., Medicine, Division on, E., Life, S., Institute for Laboratory
660 Animal, R., Board on Environmental, S., Toxicology, Committee on, V., Relevance of
661 Current Laboratory Mammalian Toxicity, T., & Expectations for New Approach Methods
662 for use in Human Health Risk, A. (2023). *Building Confidence in New Evidence Streams*
663 *for Human Health Risk Assessment: Lessons Learned from Laboratory Mammalian*
664 *Toxicity Tests*. National Academies Press.
665 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK593763/>

666 Norris, S. L., Aung, M. T., Chartres, N., & Woodruff, T. J. (2021). Evidence-to-decision
667 frameworks: a review and analysis to inform decision-making for environmental health
668 interventions. *Environmental Health*, 20(1). [https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-021-00794-](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-021-00794-z)
669 [z](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-021-00794-z)

670 Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D.,
671 Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J.
672 M., Hrobjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald,

673 S.,...Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting
674 systematic reviews. *BMJ*, 372, n71. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>

675 Panic, N., Leoncini, E., de Belvis, G., Ricciardi, W., & Boccia, S. (2013). Evaluation of the
676 endorsement of the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analysis
677 (PRISMA) statement on the quality of published systematic review and meta-analyses.
678 *PLOS ONE*, 8(12), e83138. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0083138>

679 Pavlovic, M. D., Lagisz, M., Videira, N. B., Menon, J. M. L., Vist, G. E., Omeragic, E., Morgan, R. L.,
680 Hoffmann, S., & Evidence-Based Toxicology, C. (2025). Reporting quality of systematic
681 review protocols in environmental and occupational toxicology: a meta-epidemiology
682 study protocol. *Evidence-Based Toxicology*, 3(1), 2480543.
683 <https://doi.org/10.1080/2833373X.2025.2480543>

684 Pearson, H., Ledford, H., Hutson, M., & Van Noorden, R. (2025). Exclusive: the most-cited papers
685 of the twenty-first century. *Nature*, 640(8059), 588-592.
686 <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-025-01125-9>

687 Peters, M. D. J., Marnie, C., Tricco, A. C., Pollock, D., Munn, Z., Alexander, L., McInerney, P.,
688 Godfrey, C. M., & Khalil, H. (2020). Updated methodological guidance for the conduct of
689 scoping reviews. *JBI Evid Synth*, 18(10), 2119-2126. <https://doi.org/10.11124/JBIES-20-00167>

690
691 Pieper, D., & Rombey, T. (2022). Where to prospectively register a systematic review. *Systematic*
692 *Reviews*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-021-01877-1>

693 Prasad, M. (2024). Introduction to the GRADE tool for rating certainty in evidence and
694 recommendations. *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*, 25, 101484.
695 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cegh.2023.101484>

696 Pussegoda, K., Turner, L., Garritty, C., Mayhew, A., Skidmore, B., Stevens, A., Boutron, I., Sarkis-
697 Onofre, R., Bjerre, L. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Altman, D. G., & Moher, D. (2017). Identifying
698 approaches for assessing methodological and reporting quality of systematic reviews: a
699 descriptive study. *Syst Rev*, 6(1), 117. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-017-0507-6>

700 Pussegoda, K., Turner, L., Garritty, C., Mayhew, A., Skidmore, B., Stevens, A., Boutron, I., Sarkis-
701 Onofre, R., Bjerre, L. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Altman, D. G., & Moher, D. (2017). Systematic
702 review adherence to methodological or reporting quality. *Systematic Reviews*, 6(1).
703 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-017-0527-2>

704 Radke, E. G., Mehta, S. S., Christensen, K. Y., Glenn, B., Rooney, A. A., Whaley, P., Morgan, R. L.,
705 Beverly, B. E. J., Thayer, K., Taylor, K. W., Barbic, F., Akl, E. A., & Schünemann, H. J.
706 (2026). GRADE concept article: Evaluating risk of bias in a body of evidence from studies
707 of environmental and other exposures. *Environ Int*, 213, 110310.
708 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2026.110310>

709 Ramadhan Makame, K., Sherif, M., Östlundh, L., Sándor, J., Ádám, B., & Nagy, K. (2023). Are
710 encapsulated pesticides less harmful to human health than their conventional
711 alternatives? Protocol for a systematic review of in vitro and in vivo animal model
712 studies. *Environment International*, 174, 107924.
713 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2023.107924>

714 Rethlefsen, M. L., Kirtley, S., Waffenschmidt, S., Ayala, A. P., Moher, D., Page, M. J., & Koffel, J. B.
715 (2021). PRISMA-S: an extension to the PRISMA Statement for Reporting Literature
716 Searches in Systematic Reviews. *Syst Rev*, 10(1), 39. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-020-01542-z>

717
718 Rooney, A. A., Boyles, A. L., Wolfe, M. S., Bucher, J. R., & Thayer, K. A. (2014). Systematic review
719 and evidence integration for literature-based environmental health science

720 assessments. *Environ Health Perspect*, 122(7), 711-718.
721 <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1307972>

722 Rosenberg, J., Bauchner, H., Backus, J., De Leeuw, P., Drazen, J., Frizelle, F., Godlee, F., Haug, C.,
723 James, A., Laine, C., Reyes, H., Sahni, P., & Zhaori, G. (2013). The New ICMJE
724 Recommendations. *Natl Med J India*, 26(5), 258-259.

725 Ross, J. S., Hill, K. P., Egilman, D. S., & Krumholz, H. M. (2008). Guest authorship and ghostwriting
726 in publications related to rofecoxib: a case study of industry documents from rofecoxib
727 litigation. *Jama*, 299(15), 1800-1812. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.299.15.1800>

728 Sarah, R. H., Shariful Islam, M., Zamiur Rahaman, M., Afrin, S., Rahman, M., & Saif-Ur-Rahman,
729 K. M. (2022). Pivotal role of environmental toxicants on developing infectious diseases
730 in LMICs: a protocol for a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ Open*, 12(7),
731 e058927. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2021-058927>

732 Schiavo, J. H. (2019). PROSPERO: An International Register of Systematic Review Protocols.
733 *Medical Reference Services Quarterly*, 38(2), 171-180.
734 <https://doi.org/10.1080/02763869.2019.1588072>

735 Schlusssel, M. M., Sharp, M. K., de Beyer, J. A., Kirtley, S., Logullo, P., Dhiman, P., MacCarthy, A.,
736 Koroleva, A., Speich, B., Bullock, G. S., Moher, D., & Collins, G. S. (2023). Reporting
737 guidelines used varying methodology to develop recommendations. *Journal of Clinical
738 Epidemiology*, 159, 246-256.
739 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2023.03.018>

740 Senerth, E., Tangri, N., Krammer, L., Gaby, V., Whaley, P., Johnson, G., Tsaioun, K., & Morgan, R.
741 L. (2024). Systematic review methods in environmental health: a critical interpretive
742 synthesis to inform the evolution of systematic review guidance. *Evidence-Based
743 Toxicology*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2833373x.2024.2443410>

744 Sesin, V., Judy, J. D., Kapustka, L., Opeolu, B., Ottinger, M. A., Bertsch, P. M., Wang, Y.,
745 Lazorchak, J., Smythe, T. A., & Stahl, R. G., Jr. (2023). The Importance of Fostering and
746 Funding Scientific Research, and its Relevance to Environmental Toxicology and
747 Chemistry. *Environ Toxicol Chem*, 42(3), 581-593. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.5542>

748 Shaheen, N., Shaheen, A., Ramadan, A., Hefnawy, M. T., Ramadan, A., Ibrahim, I. A., Hassanein,
749 M. E., Ashour, M. E., & Flouty, O. (2023). Appraising systematic reviews: a
750 comprehensive guide to ensuring validity and reliability. *Front Res Metr Anal*, 8,
751 1268045. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frma.2023.1268045>

752 Shamseer, L., Moher, D., Clarke, M., Ghersi, D., Liberati, A., Petticrew, M., Shekelle, P., &
753 Stewart, L. A. (2015). Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis
754 protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015: elaboration and explanation. *BMJ*, 349(jan02 1), g7647-
755 g7647. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.g7647>

756 Shea, B. J., Reeves, B. C., Wells, G., Thuku, M., Hamel, C., Moran, J., Moher, D., Tugwell, P.,
757 Welch, V., Kristjansson, E., & Henry, D. A. (2017). AMSTAR 2: a critical appraisal tool for
758 systematic reviews that include randomised or non-randomised studies of healthcare
759 interventions, or both. *BMJ*, 358, j4008. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.j4008>

760 Sheehan, M. C., & Lam, J. (2015). Use of Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis in Environmental
761 Health Epidemiology: a Systematic Review and Comparison with Guidelines. *Current
762 Environmental Health Reports*, 2(3), 272-283. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40572-015-0062-z>

763 Siebert, M., Caquelin, L., Madera, M., Acosta-Dighero, R., Naudet, F., & Roqué, M. (2023).
764 Assessing the magnitude of changes from protocol to publication—a survey on Cochrane
765 and non-Cochrane Systematic Reviews [Article]. *PeerJ*, 11.
766 <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.16016>

767

768 Siedler, M. R., Harris, K. N., Rodriguez, C., Lewis, M. H., Semidey-Lamadrid, P., Stratton, M. T.,
769 Blacutt, M., Hosseini, Z., Falck-Ytter, Y., Mustafa, R. A., Sultan, S., Dahm, P., Morgan, R.
770 L., & Murad, M. H. (2024). Certainty of Evidence Assessment in Systematic Reviews
771 Published by High-Impact Sports Science Journals: A Meta-epidemiological Study. *Sports*
772 *Medicine*, 54(2), 473-484. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-023-01941-x>

773 Siontis, K. C., Hernandez-Boussard, T., & Ioannidis, J. P. (2013). Overlapping meta-analyses on
774 the same topic: survey of published studies. *BMJ*, 347, f4501.
775 <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.f4501>

776 Speich, B., Odutayo, A., Peckham, N., Ooms, A., Stokes, J. R., Saccilotto, R., Gryaznov, D., von
777 Niederhäusern, B., Copsey, B., Altman, D. G., Briel, M., & Hopewell, S. (2022). A
778 longitudinal assessment of trial protocols approved by research ethics committees: The
779 Adherence to SPIrit REcommendations in the UK (ASPIRE-UK) study. *Trials*, 23(1), 601.
780 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-022-06516-1>

781 Stewart, L., Moher, D., & Shekelle, P. (2012). Why prospective registration of systematic reviews
782 makes sense. *Systematic Reviews*, 1(1), 7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2046-4053-1-7>

783 Struijs, F., Hooijmans, C. R., Buijs, M., Dahan, A., Hoffmann, S., Kiffen, R., Mandrioli, D., Menon,
784 J., Ritskes-Hoitinga, M., Roeleveld, N., De Ruijter, A., Scheffer, G. J., Schlünssen, V., &
785 Scheepers, P. T. J. (2023). Establishing a health-based recommended occupational
786 exposure limit for isoflurane using experimental animal data: a systematic review
787 protocol. *Systematic Reviews*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-023-02331-0>

788 Tawfik, G. M., Giang, H. T. N., Ghozy, S., Altibi, A. M., Kandil, H., Le, H. H., Eid, P. S., Radwan, I.,
789 Makram, O. M., Hien, T. T. T., Sherif, M., Hossain, A. S., Thang, T. L. L., Puljak, L., Salem,
790 H., Numair, T., Moji, K., & Huy, N. T. (2020). Protocol registration issues of systematic
791 review and meta-analysis studies: a survey of global researchers. *BMC Med Res*
792 *Methodol*, 20(1), 213. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-020-01094-9>

793 Uter, W., Johansen, J. D., Havmose, M. S., Kezic, S., van der Molen, H. F., Macan, J., Babić, Ž.,
794 Turk, R., Symanzik, C., & John, S. M. (2021). Protocol for a systematic review on systemic
795 and skin toxicity of important hazardous hair and nail cosmetic ingredients in
796 hairdressers. *BMJ Open*, 11(12), e050612. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2021-050612>

797

798 Vaccari, C., El Dib, R., & de Camargo, J. L. V. (2017). Paraquat and Parkinson's disease: a
799 systematic review protocol according to the OHAT approach for hazard identification.
800 *Syst Rev*, 6(1), 98. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-017-0491-x>

801 Van Der Braak, K., Ghannad, M., Orelino, C., Heus, P., Damen, J. A. A., Spijker, R., Robinson, K.,
802 Lund, H., & Hooft, L. (2022). The score after 10 years of registration of systematic review
803 protocols. *Systematic Reviews*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-022-02053-9>

804 Van Der Braak, K., Heus, P., Orelino, C., Netterström-Wedin, F., Robinson, K. A., Lund, H., & Hooft,
805 L. (2023). Perspectives on systematic review protocol registration: a survey amongst
806 stakeholders in the clinical research publication process. *Systematic Reviews*, 12(1).
807 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-023-02405-z>

808 van der Braak, K., Heus, P., Orelino, C., Netterström-Wedin, F., Robinson, K. A., Lund, H., & Hooft,
809 L. (2023). Perspectives on systematic review protocol registration: a survey amongst
810 stakeholders in the clinical research publication process. *Syst Rev*, 12(1), 234.
811 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-023-02405-z>

812 van der Zalm, A. J., Barroso, J., Browne, P., Casey, W., Gordon, J., Henry, T. R., Kleinstreuer, N. C.,
813 Lowit, A. B., Perron, M., & Clippinger, A. J. (2022). A framework for establishing scientific
814 confidence in new approach methodologies. *Archives of Toxicology*, 96(11), 2865-2879.
815 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00204-022-03365-4>

816 van Luijk, J. A. K. R., Popa, M., Swinkels, J., Menon, J. M. L., Alkema, W., Roeleveld, N.,
817 Hoffmann, S. E., Schlünssen, V., Mandrioli, D., Ritskes-Hoitinga, M., & Scheepers, P. T. J.
818 (2019). Establishing a health-based recommended occupational exposure limit for
819 nitrous oxide using experimental animal data – A systematic review protocol.
820 *Environmental Research*, 178, 108711.
821 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.108711>

822 Whaley, P., Aiassa, E., Beausoleil, C., Beronius, A., Bilotta, G., Boobis, A., de Vries, R., Hanberg,
823 A., Hoffmann, S., Hunt, N., Kwiatkowski, C. F., Lam, J., Lipworth, S., Martin, O., Randall,
824 N., Rhomberg, L., Rooney, A. A., Schünemann, H. J., Wikoff, D.,...Halsall, C. (2020).
825 Recommendations for the conduct of systematic reviews in toxicology and
826 environmental health research (COSTER). *Environment International*, 143, 105926.
827 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105926>

828 Whaley, P., Letcher, R. J., Covaci, A., & Alcock, R. (2016). Raising the standard of systematic
829 reviews published in *Environment International*. *Environment International*, 97, 274-
830 276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2016.08.007>

831 WHO. (2024). Air pollution. In: Compendium of WHO and other UN guidance in health and
832 environment. In: WHO. <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/378095>

833 Wikoff, D., & Fitch, S. (2024). Evidence-Based Methods in Toxicology. In *Human and Ecological*
834 *Risk Assessment* (pp. 1131-1148).
835 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119742975.ch32>

836 Wikoff, D., Lewis, R. J., Erraguntla, N., Franzen, A., & Foreman, J. (2020). Facilitation of risk
837 assessment with evidence-based methods – A framework for use of systematic mapping
838 and systematic reviews in determining hazard, developing toxicity values, and
839 characterizing uncertainty. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 118, 104790.
840 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2020.104790>

841 Woodruff, T. J., & Sutton, P. (2014). The Navigation Guide systematic review methodology: a
842 rigorous and transparent method for translating environmental health science into
843 better health outcomes. *Environ Health Perspect*, 122(10), 1007-1014.
844 <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1307175>

845 Zhang, Y. X., Liu, Y. P., Miao, S. S., Liu, X. D., Ma, S. M., & Qu, Z. Y. (2021). Exposure to persistent
846 organic pollutants and thyroid cancer risk: a study protocol of systematic review and
847 meta-analysis. *BMJ Open*, 11(8), e048451. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-048451>
848

849